

ETHNOBOTANICAL STUDIES OF CHATROO AREA OF DISTRICT KISHTWAR (NORTH WESTERN HIMALAYAS), JAMMU AND KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

The present research documents the ethnobotanical wealth of Chatroo, District Kishtwar, located in the northwestern Himalayas of Jammu and Kashmir. Extensive field surveys were carried out to document the indigenous knowledge of medicinal and economic plants. A total of 89 species belonging to 52 families were identified, including herbs, shrubs, trees, climbers, gymnosperms, and pteridophytes. These plants are used for diverse purposes such as treating digestive, respiratory, and excretory disorders, as well as in religious practices, food, fodder, and fuel. The study highlights the vital role of ethnobotany in rural and tribal communities and emphasizes the urgent need for conservation and sustainable utilization of this biodiversity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Life on Earth is sustained by plants, which form the basis of ecosystems and human survival. Ethnobotany is the study of the traditional knowledge of plants and their uses. It has gained renewed importance in the modern era. Communities worldwide, including those in India, have long relied on plants for food, medicine, shelter, and cultural practices. In India, systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani draw from traditional plant knowledge. WHO estimates suggest that up to 80% of populations in Asia and Africa depend on traditional medicines (World Health Organization, 1983; World Health Organization, 2013).

Jammu and Kashmir, with its unique Himalayan ecosystems, harbors rich biodiversity. Kishtwar district, particularly Tehsil Chatroo, remains underexplored despite its wealth of

flora. The rural and tribal communities of the region possess remarkable knowledge of plants, acquired over generations, and continue to depend on them for healthcare and livelihood.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Traditional plant use has deep historical roots, with records in ancient texts such as the Rigveda, Atharvaveda, and Ayurveda (Jain, 1981). Early works like *Flora Indica* (Hooker & Thomson, 1855) and *Flora of British India* (Hooker, 1872) laid the foundation for Indian botanical documentation. Richard Evans Schultes pioneered ethnobotany globally, while V. K. Jain (1981) and E. K. Janaki Ammal advanced its study in India.

Numerous studies have documented Himalayan ethnobotany. Trak & Giri (2017) investigated Gujjar and Bakarwal tribes in Kishtwar, identifying 36 ethnomedicinal species. Rather & Baba (2015) reviewed 81 medicinal plants in Kashmir, noting threats of overexploitation. Similar studies in Himachal Pradesh, Ladakh, and other districts of Jammu and Kashmir revealed diverse uses of plants, especially in healthcare and subsistence (Dar *et al.*, 2011; Malik *et al.*, 2015; Lone & Bhardwaj, 2013). These works underscore the importance of documentation and conservation of ethnomedicinal knowledge.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The research was conducted in Tehsil Chatroo of Kishtwar District (33.31°N, 75.76°E), situated at an elevation of 3000–15,000 ft in the northwestern Himalayas. The region is characterized by temperate to alpine climate, with average annual rainfall of 994 mm and snowfall in winter. Major villages surveyed included Chatroo, Chingam, Horna, Drubeel, Singpora, and high-altitude pastures such as Sinthon Top and Bonda.

Figure: showing study area (in green).

Methodology

Extensive field surveys were conducted, involving semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and direct observations. Informants included local villagers, tribals (Gujjars, Bakarwals), and elderly persons with traditional knowledge. Plant specimens were collected, photographed, and prepared as herbarium vouchers following standard techniques. Identification was carried out using regional floras (Flora of British India, Hooker, 1872; Flora of Jammu and Kashmir, BSI, 2002; Flowers of the Himalayas, Polunin & Stainton, 1997).

4. OBSERVATIONS

The ethnobotanical survey conducted in Tehsil Chatroo, District Kishtwar, documented a total of 89 plant species belonging to 52 families. These include herbs (62%), shrubs (18%), trees (15%), and climbers and others (5%), reflecting the dominance of herbaceous flora in the temperate and alpine regions of the Himalayas.

Notable Documented Species

Daphne oleoides ; Family: Thymelaeaceae ; Local name: Sonai

Uses: Leaves used to induce abortion; roots purgative; bark/leaf infusion for skin infections.

Jurinea dolomiaea ; Family: Asteraceae ; Local name: Dhup Uses: Roots used as incense (dhoop); root juice for fever.

Calendula arvensis ; Family: Asteraceae ; Local name: Hamesh bahar

Uses: Oil antibacterial, antifungal; flowers for spasm, fever, anaemia, constipation.

Taraxacum officinale ; Family: Asteraceae ; Local name: Hand

Uses: Tea from leaves; diuretic, antibacterial; leaf paste with salt & turmeric for bone fractures.

Saussurea costus ; Family: Asteraceae ; Local name: Koth

Uses: Rhizome for joint/back pain, ulcers, dysentery, fever; root anodyne, antibacterial, aphrodisiac.

Bergenia ciliata ; Family: Saxifragaceae ; Local name: Zakhme hayat

Uses: Root tonic for fevers, diarrhoea, lung infections; leaves/roots for ulcers, intestinal pain, wound healing.

Rheum emodi ; Family: Polygonaceae ; Local name: Panchalan Uses: Rhizome for rheumatism, joint dislocation, boils, wounds.

Aconitum heterophyllum ; Family: Ranunculaceae ; Local name: Pateesh

Uses: Joint pain, gout, inflammation, throat infection, abdominal pain, diabetes; antidote for snake bite.

Arnebia benthamii ; Family: Boraginaceae ; Local name: Kah zaban

Uses: Increases lactation; extract for fever & abdominal pain; antifungal, wound healing.

Malva sylvestris ; Family: Malvaceae ; Local name: Sochal Uses: Seeds for cough/fever; leaves & stems as vegetables.

Mentha longifolia ; Family: Apiaceae ; Local name: Jangli pudina

Uses: Leaf infusion for fever, headache, digestive disorders; stimulant, coolant.

Solanum nigrum ; Family: Solanaceae ; Local name: Kambli kul

Uses: Fruits edible; used for indigestion, jaundice, constipation; root juice for cough/asthma.

Picrorhiza kurroa Family: Plantaginaceae ; Local name: Koud;

Uses: Jaundice, liver infections, asthma, indigestion, arthritis; external paste for rheumatism.

Podophyllum hexandrum ; Family: Berberidaceae ; Local name: Van wangun

Uses: Purgative; vaginal warts; ulcers, wounds; rhizome for typhoid & skin diseases.

Digitalis purpurea ; Family: Scrophulariaceae ; Local name: Loshzata Uses: Leaves treat cardiac disorders; paste for sores/wounds.

Juglans regia ; Family: Juglandaceae ; Local name: Dun

Uses: Nuts edible & oil; bark/root bark anthelmintic; twigs used as miswak for teeth cleaning.

Ocimum basilicum ; Family: Lamiaceae ; Local name: Babre byoul

Uses: Digestive aid, for fever, insomnia, depression, colds; antimicrobial & antioxidant.

Rauvolfia serpentina ; Family: Apocynaceae ; Local name: Sarpgandha

Uses: Lowers blood pressure; used in hysteria, insomnia, hypertension; snake bite remedy.

Urtica dioica ; Family: Urticaceae ; Local name: Soi

Uses: For jaundice, rheumatism, arthritis, anaemia; anti-dandruff, diuretic, anti-asthmatic.

Ficus carica ; Family: Moraceae ; Local name: Anjeer

Uses: Fruit edible; lowers BP; boosts heart health; anticancer; leaves/bark for liver & skin.

Papaver somniferum ; Family: Papaveraceae ; Local name: Khash khash Uses: Seeds/oil for cough, cancer; astringent, anodyne.

Inula racemosa ; Family: Asteraceae ; Local name: Poshkar

Uses: Root for bronchitis, rheumatism; diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic.

Adiantum capillus-veneris ; Family: Adiantaceae ; Local name: Gauthier

Uses: Anti-diabetic, analgesic, wound healing, anti-asthmatic; used against spleen swelling.

Raphanus sativus ; Family: Brassicaceae ; Local name: Mooj

Uses: Leaves as vegetable; edible root; used for jaundice, immunity, piles.

Arisaema jacquemontii ; Family: Araceae ; Local name: Hapath makai Uses: Rhizome paste for muscular strength; used in skin problems.

Atropa belladonna ; Family: Solanaceae ; Local name: Belladonna

Uses: Reduces respiratory distress; analgesic; reduces stress & anxiety.

Coriandrum sativum ; Family: Apiaceae ; Local name: Dhaniya

Uses: Leaves in cooking; used for IBS, loss of appetite, haemorrhoids.

Viola odorata ; Family: Violaceae ; Local name: Bunafsha Uses: Flowers used in kahwa for cough, sore throat, fever.

Allium sativum ; Family: Amaryllidaceae ; Local name: Ruhn (Garlic) Uses: Antioxidant; reduces cholesterol; heart health; anticancer.

Trillium govanianum ; Family: Melanthiaceae ; Local name: Naag chatri Uses: Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anticancer; trade prohibited.

Colchicum luteum ; Family: Liliaceae ; Local name: Suranjan shiri

Uses: Used in Ayurveda for liver/spleen inflammation; sprinkled on wounds for healing. Plant Parts Used

- Roots and rhizomes are most frequently used, e.g., *Saussurea costus*, *Picrorhiza kurroa*.
- Leaves are used in making teas, decoctions, and poultices (*Taraxacum officinale*, *Urtica dioica*).
- Fruits/seeds are consumed directly or used medicinally (*Juglans regia*).
- Bark and wood are used for medicinal and construction purposes (*Cedrus deodara*).
- Flowers and whole plants e.g., *Calendula arvensis*.

Mode of Preparation and Administration

- Decoctions and teas were the most common oral remedies.
- Powdered roots/rhizomes were used against digestive and respiratory disorders.
- Poultices and pastes applied externally for bone fractures, wounds, and swellings.
- Smoke and oils occasionally used for joint pains and rituals.

Altitudinal Distribution

Species were distributed from 1500 m to 4500 m above sea level. Low-altitude villages (1500–2200 m) had fruit trees and herbs (*Juglans regia*), while high-altitude pastures (>3500 m) supported alpine species (*Saussurea costus*, *Jurinea dolomiaea*, *Aconitum heterophyllum*).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ethnobotanical diversity of Chatroo reflects a dependence of local populations on

plant resources. Medicinal uses dominated, followed by food, fodder, and fuel. Herbal remedies were applied both orally (decoctions, teas, infusions) and externally (pastes, poultices). The knowledge is largely oral, passed across generations, especially among nomadic and tribal communities (Lone & Bhardwaj, 2013).

The survey revealed that herbs were the dominant life form, highlighting their importance in healthcare. Overexploitation and unregulated trade pose threats to valuable species such as *Saussurea costus* (Koth), *Picrorhiza kurroa* (Koud), and *Podophyllum hexandrum* (Van Wangun) (Rather & Baba, 2015). Unsustainable extraction, deforestation, and habitat loss are pushing many plants toward endangered status (Samant & Pant, 2006).

The findings highlight the dual role of ethnobotany: preserving traditional wisdom while providing leads for modern pharmacological research. However, conservation measures—both in situ and ex situ—are urgently needed to prevent biodiversity loss. Awareness campaigns, community participation, and strict implementation of conservation laws are crucial (Dar et al., 2015).]

Fig: Graph showing number of families, species of different group.

6. CONCLUSION

The Chatroo region of Kishtwar hosts a rich diversity of ethnobotanically significant plants. Traditional knowledge continues to serve as a primary healthcare system for rural and tribal communities. Documentation of this knowledge is vital to preserve cultural heritage and provide a scientific basis for future drug discoveries. Immediate measures for sustainable use and conservation are required to protect this ethnobotanical wealth.

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